

Evaluation of New Substituent Parameters to Explain ^{13}C Chemical Shift for *para*-Substituents in Benzene Ring

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The ^{13}C chemical shift data of 1,4-disubstituted benzenes have been used to evaluate *para*-substituent constants (α_X^4 and β_X^4) and their applicability has been examined in 39 different sets of data. These parameters have been found highly suitable to correlate the ^{13}C chemical shifts of aromatic, aliphatic and heterocyclic systems.

EXTENSIVE correlation of ^{13}C chemical shifts in mono-substituted benzenes with Hammett's σ^1 constants has been reported by Spiesscke and Schneider² for the first time following the work of Lauterber^{3,4}. Other parameters⁵ used for the correlation are σ_p^+ , σ_p^- and σ_R^+ . Good correlations have been observed⁶ with σ_p^+ for substituent at *para*-position. However, analysis of extensive experimental data shows that Hammett equation fails for charged substituents⁷. Correlations of substituent chemical shift for *ortho*- and *meta*-substituents in benzene with σ have been found to be unsatisfactory⁸. Use of single parameter for correlation with substituent chemical shift has been criticised. The reason for the failure of the use of one substituent parameter is that the constituent factors (polar and mesomeric) sometimes differ widely in magnitude in different systems.

Taft⁹ applied dual substituent parameters with inductive (field) effect (σ_I) and resonance effect (σ_R). Topsom¹⁰ has summarised the advantages of the use of dual substituent parameters (DSP) analysis in the interpretation of spectroscopic data. DSP analysis of benzene substituent chemical shift for *para*-position has been made with varieties of substituent parameters. Parameters used are σ_I and σ_R^+ by Taft *et al.*^{9,10}, F and R (Swain-Lupton's parameter) by Bodner and Todd¹¹, σ_I and σ_R by Coulson¹². Godfrey¹³ has introduced three new parameters, F (a coulombic field effect, having no relation with traditional field parameters), T (a charge transfer effect) and S (overlap field). Correlation of benzene chemical shift values with F and R (Swain-Lupton's parameter) and Q^{14} (a semiempirical parameter) have been found to be successful¹⁵. Dewar *et al.*¹⁷ have proposed a triple parameter model involving contribution from field (F), mesomeric (M) and mesomeric-field (MF) effects to correlate the substituent effect and is known as FMMF method. However, the correlation of benzene chemical shift by FMMF method has been found to be unsatisfactory¹⁶. Reynolds and Hammer¹⁸ have shown the limitations of FMMF method. In this work an

attempt has been made to derive some new substituent parameters for substituents at position-4 in the benzene ring using the nmr chemical shift values.

Evaluation of parameters :

To facilitate the statistical analysis in this work the ^{13}C chemical shift values of C-4 in 1,4-disubstituted benzene²⁰ (1) have been given in Table 1. This data set is called 'training set'. An examination

of the training set reveals that (i) the C-4 chemical shifts of a column-set vary in the same order for all substituents at position-4, (varying Y) for all values of X, (ii) the chemical shift values of a row-set also depends on the nature of the substituent, X. To explain the chemical shift values (δ) equation (1) is proposed, which describes the influence of the variance of a substituent, X with respect to H for the same substituent Y at C-4.

$$\delta_{XY} = \alpha_X^4 \delta_{HY} + \beta_X^4 \quad (1)$$

In this equation δ_{XY} is the ^{13}C chemical shift values of compounds with varying Y substituent and fixed X, δ_{HY} is the chemical shift values of such compounds, where X=H. The α_X^4 is the sensitivity index for the *para*-substituent X on the C-13 chemical shift at C-4 and the β_X^4 value is constant for a particular column and varies with the nature of the substituent, X. Values of α_X^4 and β_X^4 are calculated from the data set given in Table 1 by least square method in a DCM-1101 microcomputer. The values of α_X^4 and β_X^4 are given in Table 2 along with the other statistical parameters.

General feature of parameters :

The α_X^4 and β_X^4 values thus evaluated are found to have almost an inverse relationship to each other. Values of α_X^4 are less than one for electron donating substituents, like NMe₂, NH₂, OMe, F, Cl, Br and Me, and more than one for electron withdrawing substituent, like CF₃, CN, COOEt, COMe, NO₂ and CHO, the hydrogen having the value one.

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TABLE 1—TRAINING SET

Sl. no.		NMe ₂	NH ₂	OMe	F	Cl	Br	Me	H	CF ₃	CN	COOEt	COMe	NO ₂	CHO
1.	NMe ₂	144.08	144.81	145.71	147.44	148.98	149.47	148.80	150.59	152.14	152.38	153.16	153.81	154.01	154.28
2.	NH ₂	137.87	138.55	139.87	142.86	144.86	145.89	143.70	146.22	149.35	150.44	150.09	151.08	152.43	152.49
3.	OMe	152.04	152.69	153.84	155.68	158.16	158.68	157.24	159.52	163.00	162.76	163.16	163.36	164.57	164.57
4.	F	155.82	156.28	157.19	158.75	161.22	161.77	161.00	162.82	164.61	164.96	165.61	165.61	166.20	166.48
5.	Cl	121.81	123.12	125.50	129.09	132.03	133.17	131.03	134.24	138.12	139.48	139.13	139.38	141.31	140.98
6.	Br	108.51	110.17	112.77	116.48	120.27	121.03	119.04	122.44	126.40	127.95	127.78	128.27	129.96	129.72
7.	Me	126.67	127.73	129.87	133.27	136.18	136.71	134.68	137.88	142.01	143.61	143.36	143.75	145.89	145.45
8.	H	116.62	118.51	120.63	123.92	126.41	126.81	125.26	128.31	131.98	132.66	132.73	132.98	134.49	134.33
9.	CF ₃	117.80	120.01	122.85	126.45	129.08	129.72	127.83	130.62	133.97	134.53	134.21	134.33	135.91	135.62
10.	CN	97.24	99.81	103.87	108.54	110.76	111.22	109.21	112.35	116.04	116.66	116.23	116.28	118.29	117.84
11.	COOEt	117.30	120.01	122.83	126.71	128.85	129.29	127.73	130.45	133.65	134.24	134.09	134.19	135.84	135.11
12.	COMe	125.21	127.68	130.20	133.46	135.30	135.74	134.57	137.00	139.62	139.77	140.00	140.11	141.37	141.19
13.	NO ₂	137.16	139.18	141.50	144.42	146.44	147.05	146.12	148.26	149.96	150.01	150.49	150.35	151.03	151.13
14.	CHO	125.01	127.88	129.96	132.96	137.98	135.06	134.14	136.37	139.65	138.70	139.19	138.94	140.04	140.01

TABLE 2—VALUES OF SUBSTITUENT PARAMETERS

α_x^+ AND β_x^+ AS PER EQUATION (1)

Sl. no.	Substituent	α_x^+	β_x^+	γ	SD
1.	NMe ₂	0.80	30.37	0.998	0.9151
2.	NH ₂	0.84	30.61	0.997	1.1533
3.	OMe	0.92	17.08	0.999	0.7320
4.	F	0.98	6.94	0.999	0.6679
5.	Cl	0.99	2.58	0.998	0.9144
6.	Br	0.99	2.00	1.000	0.1779
7.	Me	0.97	6.66	1.000	0.3186
8.	H	1.00	0.0	1.000	—
9.	CF ₃	1.04	-9.11	0.999	0.7049
10.	CN	1.05	-10.75	0.997	1.2069
11.	COOEt	1.03	-8.09	0.998	0.9911
12.	COMe	1.03	-8.27	0.997	1.1879
13.	NO ₂	1.05	-12.68	0.992	1.8019
14.	CHO	1.04	-10.97	0.995	1.5107

The β_x^+ values do not exhibit any regularity except that electron donor substituents show positive values and electron acceptor substituents show negative values, Zero being the value for hydrogen as the substituent. The β_x^+ values have a greater variance than the α_x^+ values. To examine, if these α_x^+

and β_x^+ values have any collinearity with other known parameters (P), equation (2) has been written.

$$\alpha_x^+ \text{ or } \beta_x^+ = AP + B \quad (2)$$

Parameters (P) correlated are Swain-Lupton's F, R; σ_F^+ , Taft's σ_I , σ_R and E_s^{+1} . In equation (2), B is the intercept and A is the coefficient of the parameter P. Again α_x^+ and β_x^+ are individually correlated with F and R and σ_I and σ_R by a DSP equation (3),

$$\alpha_x^+ \text{ or } \beta_x^+ = A_1 P_1 + A_2 P_2 + B' \quad (3)$$

where A_1 and A_2 are coefficients of parameters P_1 and P_2 , respectively, and B' is the intercept. The statistical parameters derived from equations (2) and (3) are given in Tables 3 and 4, respectively.

A close analysis of Table 3 and 4 reveals that both α_x^+ and β_x^+ have a better relation with resonance than field effect. A DSP analysis, though improves the correlation, does not bring the level of correlation to 0.99. Further addition of useful parameters involving magnetic effect, charge density effect may improve the correlations. Since the quantification of these effects sometime becomes a vexing problem, it is proposed that α_x^+ and β_x^+ can be taken as useful parameters to predict the chemical shift values.

TABLE 3—RELATION OF α_x^+ AND β_x^+ WITH DIFFERENT PARAMETERS USING EQUATION (3)

Sl. no.	Parameter	A	γ	SD	B	t	n	
1.	α_x^+	F	0.1418	0.7006	0.521	0.9139	0.0528	14
2.	Do	R	0.1815	0.9010	0.0887	1.009	0.032	14
3.	Do	σ_F^+	0.0828	0.855	0.0386	0.9781	0.0391	13
4.	Do	σ_I	0.1648	0.5446	0.0613	0.9319	0.0691	14
5.	Do	σ_R	0.2330	0.9014	0.08161	1.0078	0.0820	14
6.	Do	E_s^{+1}	-0.03584	0.4581	0.0618	0.9469	0.06278	10
7.	β_x^+	F	-29.1868	0.6929	10.9587	17.1849	0.7658	14
8.	Do	R	-37.8114	0.9018	6.5678	-2.4391	0.4589	14
9.	Do	σ_I	-82.9624	0.5249	12.9367	18.2635	0.9040	14
10.	Do	σ_R	-50.5578	0.9395	5.2028	-2.8184	0.3635	14
11.	Do	E_s^{+1}	7.972	0.5005	12.1612	11.6399	0.9855	10

TABLE 4—RELATION OF α_x^4 AND β_x^4 WITH F, R AND σ_I , σ_R AS PER EQUATION (3)

Sl. no.			A ₁	B ₁	r	SD	Q	n
1.	α_x^4	F, R	0.0788	0.1474	0.9571	0.0220	0.9161	14
2.	α_x^4	σ_I, σ_R	0.0920	0.2095	0.9469	0.0245	0.9758	14
3.	β_x^4	F, R	-14.7217	-31.006	0.9584	4.7864	5.8251	14
4.	β_x^4	σ_I, σ_R	-17.0584	-46.2501	0.9747	3.5434	3.6229	14

TABLE 5—TRAINING SETS AND TEST SETS

Train- ing set	
1.	$\delta^{13}C$ - 1 of <i>para</i> -substituted NN dimethylaniline ^a
2.	$\delta^{13}C$ - 1 of <i>para</i> -substituted aniline ^a
3.	$\delta^{13}C$ - 1 of <i>para</i> -substituted anisole ^a
4.	$\delta^{13}C$ - 1 of <i>para</i> -substituted fluorobenzene ^a
5.	$\delta^{13}C$ - 1 of <i>para</i> -substituted chlorobenzene ^a
6.	$\delta^{13}C$ - 1 of <i>para</i> -substituted bromobenzene ^a
7.	$\delta^{13}C$ - 1 of <i>para</i> -substituted toluene ^a
8.	$\delta^{13}C$ - 1 of <i>para</i> -substituted benzene ^a
9.	$\delta^{13}C$ - 1 of <i>para</i> -substituted trifluoromethylbenzene ^a
10.	$\delta^{13}C$ - 1 of <i>para</i> -substituted cyanobenzene ^a
11.	$\delta^{13}C$ - 1 of <i>para</i> -substituted ethylbenzoate ^a
12.	$\delta^{13}C$ - 1 of <i>para</i> -substituted acetophenone ^a
13.	$\delta^{13}C$ - 1 of <i>para</i> -substituted nitrobenzene ^a
14.	$\delta^{13}C$ - 1 of <i>para</i> -substituted benzaldehyde ^a
Test sets	
15.	$\delta^{13}C$ - 9 for 6-substituted 2-aminobenzothiazoles ^b
16.	$\delta^{13}C$ - 9 for 6-substituted 2-methylbenzothiazoles ^b
17.	$\delta^{13}C$ - 4 for 2-substituted benzothiazoles ^b
18.	$\delta^{13}C$ - 6 for 2-substituted benzothiazoles ^b
19.	$\delta^{13}C$ - 8 for 2-substituted benzothiazoles ^b
20.	$\delta^{13}C$ - 1 for 4-substituted phenylacetylenes ^c
21.	$\delta^{13}C$ - 3 for 1-x-isoquinolines ^d
22.	$\delta^{13}C$ - 1 for 4-x-isoquinolines ^d
23.	$\delta^{13}C$ - 1 for 4-x-substituted benzotrifluorides ^e
24.	$\delta^{13}C$ - 1 for <i>para</i> -substituted acetophenones ^f
25.	$\delta^{13}C$ - 1 for <i>para</i> -substituted benzylbenzenes ^g
26.	$\delta^{13}C$ - 5 for <i>ortho</i> -substituted phenols in cyclohexane ^h
27.	$\delta^{13}C$ - 5 for <i>ortho</i> -substituted phenols in DMSO ^h
28.	$\delta^{13}C$ - 5 for 2-substituted pyridines ⁱ
29.	$\delta^{13}C$ - 6 for 3-substituted pyridines ⁱ
30.	$\delta^{13}C$ - 5 for 2-substituted pyrimidines ⁱ
31.	$\delta^{13}C$ - 1 for 4-substituted phenylvinylethers ^k
32.	$\delta^{13}C$ - 1 for 4-substituted phenylvinylsulfides ^k
33.	$\delta^{13}C$ - 1 for 4-substituted phenylvinylselenides ^k
34.	$\delta^{13}C$ - 4 for <i>para</i> -substituted benzamide ^l
35.	$\delta^{13}C$ - 1 for 4-substituted styrenes ^m
36.	$\delta^{13}C$ for 4-substituted α -methylstyrenes ⁿ
37.	$\delta^{13}C$ for 4-substituted α -t-butylstyrenes ⁿ
38.	$\delta^{13}C$ - 9 for 6-substituted benzothiazoles ^o
39.	$\delta^{13}C$ - 8 for 5-substituted 2-methylbenzothiazoles ^o

a. Ref. 20. b. Ref. 21. c. Ref. 18.

d. A. VAN VELDHUIZEN, M. VAN DIJK and G. M. SANDERS, *Org. Magn. Reson.*, 1980, 13, 105. e. R. A. NEWMARK and J. H. HILL, *Org. Magn. Reson.*, 1977, 9, 589. f. T. DRAKENBERG, J. M. SOMMER and R. JOST, *Org. Magn. Reson.*, 1976, 8, 579. g. Y. NAKAI, T. TAKABAYASHI and F. YAMADA, *Org. Magn. Reson.*, 1980, 13, 94. h. W. B. SMITH and T. W. PROULUX, *Org. Magn. Reson.*, 1976, 8, 205. i. V. GALASSO, *Org. Magn. Reson.*, 1979, 12, 818. j. G. J. TUNNER and G. W. H. CHEESEMAN, *Org. Magn. Reson.*, 1976, 8, 357. k. W. F. REYNOLDS and R. A. MCLELLAN, *Can. J. Chem.*, 1977, 55, 536. l. B. M. LYNCII, *Can. J. Chem.*, 1977, 55, 541. m. G. K. HAMER, *Can. J. Chem.*, 1973, 51, 897. n. G. K. HAMER, *Can. J. Chem.*, 1973, 51, 915.

Applicabilities of parameters :

The generality of these substituent parameters (α_x^4 and β_x^4) has been examined with various data sets (set 1 to 39) using equation (4).

$$\delta_x = a\alpha_x^4 + b\beta_x^4 + \delta_x^0 \quad (4)$$

In this equation δ_x is the chemical shift values of different *para*-substituted compounds at C-4, δ_x^0 is a constant for a given set, a and b are susceptibility of α_x^4 and β_x^4 to δ_x , respectively. To see the applicability of these parameters the thirty nine sets including the training sets are given in Table 5. Statistical parameters derived from the analysis of these data when correlated with α_x^4 and β_x^4 as per equation (4) are given in Table 6. Excellent correlations are obtained in all the data sets except for sets 16, 18 and 19. These parameters (α_x^4 and β_x^4) have been used to calculate the chemical shift values of some compounds for which experimental data are not available.

For the sake of comparison, all the 39 data sets have been correlated with F, R and σ_I , σ_R for which equations (4) and (5) are written separately with the terms having the usual meaning.

$$\delta_x = pF + qR + Q \quad (5)$$

$$\delta_x = c\sigma_I + d\sigma_R + I \quad (6)$$

The statistical parameters due to these correlations have been given in Table 6. It is observed that Swain-Lupton's parameters do not work well in these sets. The parameters developed in this work, are slightly better than Taft's parameters. The f values (goodness of fit parameters) have been calculated by using the equation SD/RMS, and are given in Table 6. Taft *et al.*²⁰ have shown that f=0.06 or less is required for an acceptable fit for a data set with a critical selection of substituents.

Hence, α_x^4 and β_x^4 developed by an independent method of analysis are also good substituent parameters to correlate ^{13}C nmr chemical shift values of varieties of compounds.

TABLE 6—STATISTICAL ANALYSIS

A, with α_x^* and β_x^* parameters; B, with F and B parameters; C, with σ_x and σ_R parameters

Set		n	a/p/c	b/q/d	SD	$\sigma_x^2/Q/I$	r	f
1	A	14	-108.177	-0.745	0.2474	258.448	0.9978	0.00165
	B	14	2.686	7.861	1.667	149.499	0.896	0.0111
	C	14	2.149	12.028	0.877	150.404	0.9949	0.00514
2	A	14	-169.226	-1.146	0.266	315.789	0.9988	0.00182
	B	14	4.621	10.215	3.500	145.040	0.893	0.017
	C	14	4.708	16.591	0.761	152.187	0.9906	0.0096
3	A	14	-145.974	-0.987	0.172	305.534	0.9998	0.00108
	B	14	8.884	8.955	2.142	158.410	0.891	0.013
	C	14	8.409	15.029	0.446	159.514	0.995	0.00286
4	A	14	-116.768	-0.811	0.306	179.111	0.9973	0.00188
	B	14	2.640	8.450	1.774	161.885	0.904	0.0160
	C	14	2.141	13.894	0.410	162.63	0.995	0.0025
5	A	14	184.491	0.216	2.860	2.068	0.9981	0.0184
	B	14	6.089	13.970	2.798	132.309	0.922	0.029
	C	14	6.019	12.410	0.624	133.721	0.996	0.0046
6	A	14	-137.816	-1.390	0.221	310.171	0.9996	0.00108
	B	14	6.405	15.583	3.215	120.398	0.915	0.0264
	C	14	5.970	35.100	0.711	122.03	0.996	0.0058
7	A	14	138.396	0.230	2.885	0.368	0.9975	0.0214
	B	14	6.429	13.238	2.993	186.193	0.908	0.0217
	C	14	5.193	22.108	0.461	137.78	0.997	0.00385
8	A	14	-144.424	-1.692	0.194	272.672	0.9995	0.00152
	B	14	5.340	12.658	2.540	125.566	0.920	0.0198
	C	14	5.271	20.248	0.561	127.809	0.996	0.00432
9	A	14	-81.572	-0.791	0.408	211.915	0.998	0.0030
	B	14	5.276	12.854	2.152	128.566	0.942	0.0166
	C	14	5.683	19.556	1.031	129.568	0.987	0.00796
10	A	14	-106.477	-0.971	0.308	216.218	0.994	0.00728
	B	14	6.323	14.530	2.777	109.785	0.950	0.020
	C	14	7.171	21.741	1.424	110.800	0.9807	0.0128
11	A	14	-74.898	-7.755	0.549	205.012	0.996	0.00249
	B	14	5.284	12.741	2.064	128.319	0.945	0.0159
	C	14	5.886	19.173	1.132	129.227	0.984	0.00974
12	A	14	136.697	0.314	1.716	0.143	0.9998	0.0131
	B	14	4.398	11.384	1.870	135.149	0.941	0.0138
	C	14	4.670	17.067	1.022	135.949	0.983	0.00752
13	A	14	-41.992	-0.510	0.647	189.349	0.991	0.00441
	B	14	3.199	10.605	1.633	146.470	0.944	0.011
	C	14	3.593	15.295	1.154	147.04	0.9726	0.00786
14	A	14	-26.919	-0.454	1.055	163.015	0.979	0.00779
	B	14	4.388	10.470	1.641	134.516	0.937	0.0136
	C	14	5.058	15.264	1.318	135.101	0.952	0.0135
15	A	10	-99.123	-8.815	0.323	251.735	0.998	0.00213
	B	10	4.83	11.671	1.355	150.766	0.964	0.0089
	C	10	4.706	16.591	0.701	152.187	0.990	0.00462
16	A	9	28.896	-0.116	3.334	124.916	0.765	0.0222
	B	9	8.744	8.413	3.736	151.407	0.702	0.024
	C	9	3.856	10.533	4.104	152.375	0.624	0.027
17	A	8	56.405	0.145	0.997	65.711	0.999	0.000801
	B	8	1.405	4.447	0.707	121.233	0.947	0.00582
	C	8	1.414	5.751	1.029	121.670	0.885	0.00847
18	A	8	-21.092	-0.273	0.608	147.056	0.9798	0.00434
	B	8	3.587	5.013	0.854	124.360	0.981	0.00465
	C	8	4.142	7.594	0.570	125.055	0.982	0.0045
19	A	8	-11.718	-0.199	1.114	148.343	0.9101	0.00362
	B	8	1.971	5.370	0.750	133.813	0.960	0.00559
	C	8	1.999	6.863	1.232	134.32	0.888	0.00918
20	A	10	-112.065	-0.335	1.915	234.403	0.9994	0.00158
	B	10	5.035	13.008	1.474	120.04	0.967	0.0131
	C	10	5.134	19.427	0.756	121.880	0.9918	0.00624
21	A	5	45.167	-0.047	0.643	75.831	0.992	0.00541
	B	5	4.026	11.860	0.364	120.811	0.997	0.00306
	C	5	10.276	19.227	1.949	120.34	0.999	0.00163
22	A	5	-123.245	-0.964	0.105	275.880	0.9998	0.000704
	B	5	1.397	14.218	0.430	152.654	0.996	0.00288
	C	5	6.538	21.754	0.342	152.695	0.997	0.00229
23	A	5	-163.297	-1.235	0.144	234.433	0.9997	0.00112
	B	5	1.480	16.912	0.597	131.119	0.995	0.00409
	C	5	7.582	25.812	0.614	131.170	0.995	0.00482

NAYAK, MISHRA & BEHERA : EVALUATION OF NEW SUBSTITUENT PARAMETERS TO EXPLAIN ETC.

(Table 6 Contd.)

24	A	8	-49.640	-0.580	0.205	186.803	0.9987	0.0015
	B	8	4.125	11.541	1.569	135.226	0.941	0.0106
	C	8	9.787	14.948	0.491	137.069	0.992	0.00866
25	A	11	-133.611	-1.116	0.394	273.501	0.999	0.00288
	B	11	9.261	12.579	3.009	134.40	0.931	0.0225
	C	11	6.914	22.615	1.049	137.620	0.991	0.00767
26	A	7	-123.482	-1.098	0.202	125.294	0.999	0.00893
	B	7	7.507	13.762	3.954	-0.941	0.794	0.760
	C	7	6.089	20.167	0.5184	1.308	0.996	0.0987
27	A	8	-211.057	-1.884	0.515	211.578	0.996	0.107
	B	8	6.869	11.562	3.709	-2.221	0.785	0.769
	C	8	4.717	19.955	0.969	0.897	0.986	0.2009
28	A	7	-59.388	-0.686	0.925	186.199	0.901	0.00741
	B	7	7.148	11.759	3.690	124.272	0.865	0.0294
	C	7	5.499	18.225	1.454	125.889	0.978	0.0116
29	A	6	-84.865	-0.796	0.619	236.349	0.995	0.00436
	B	6	3.328	13.261	1.919	160.128	0.959	0.0129
	C	6	3.509	20.210	1.269	151.978	0.992	0.0085
30	A	7	81.993	0.0412	0.462	89.917	0.997	0.00388
	B	7	3.659	14.294	1.620	121.207	0.965	0.0135
	C	7	8.521	17.460	2.422	120.494	0.920	0.020
31	A	7	-120.652	-0.860	0.288	277.063	0.998	0.00186
	B	7	1.227	13.931	0.326	156.649	0.986	0.0067
	C	7	3.197	15.871	0.59	156.62	0.991	0.0048
32	A	9	-117.913	-1.468	0.512	912.117	0.998	0.00488
	B	9	8.530	17.860	2.546	130.506	0.958	0.198
	C	9	9.785	28.965	1.01	187.427	0.991	0.0077
33	A	8	-221.975	-1.667	0.445	351.723	0.999	0.00356
	B	8	8.281	19.285	2.777	125.813	0.959	0.022
	C	8	8.781	18.701	0.674	128.774	0.998	0.0051
34	A	6	2098.845	11.154	2.547	-1969.484	0.994	0.020
	B	6	-12.477	-62.217	11.606	189.825	0.570	0.0911
	C	6	-8.884	-52.963	8.875	130.040	0.939	0.0658
35	A	10	-92.183	-0.816	0.247	229.517	0.998	0.001788
	B	10	4.860	13.523	1.371	135.094	0.954	0.0099
	C	10	4.477	16.937	0.416	137.078	0.996	0.0027
36	A	6	-87.744	-0.867	0.144	238.793	0.999	0.00103
	B	6	5.976	16.128	2.514	138.787	0.999	0.0175
	C	6	7.155	32.116	0.332	141.135	0.998	0.0024
37	A	7	-125.258	-1.01008	0.157	268.401	0.999	0.000966
	B	7	6.061	17.027	2.328	110.784	0.998	0.0163
	C	7	7.213	23.832	0.435	143.267	0.996	0.0031
38	A	9	-0.602	-0.271	0.501	153.07	0.992	0.0186
	B	9	7.711	6.207	3.269	150.425	0.806	0.0213
	C	9	10.917	7.807	3.702	151.03	0.742	0.0241
39	A	7	-78.049	-0.848	0.148	213.172	0.999	0.0011
	B	7	6.860	15.287	1.974	182.01	0.974	0.0148
	C	7	5.972	23.482	1.584	184.45	0.984	0.0116

References

1. L. P. HAMMETT, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1937, 59, 96.
2. H. SPIESHECKE and W. G. SCHNIDER, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1961, 35, 781.
3. P. C. LAUTERBER, *Ann. N. Y. Acad. Sci.*, 1958, 70, 841.
4. P. C. LAUTERBER, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1961, 83, 1846.
5. E. EHRENSON, R. T. C. BROWNLEE and R. W. TAFT, *Prog. Phys. Org. Chem.*, 1973, 10, 1.
6. E. M. SCHULMAN, K. A. CHRISTENSEN, D. M. GRANT and C. WALLING, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1974, 39, 2686.
7. A. J. HOFNAGEL, M. A. HOFNAGEL and B. M. WEPSTER, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1978, 43, 4720.
8. R. D. TOPSOM, *Prog. Phys. Org. Chem.*, 1976, 12, 1.
9. J. BROMILOW, R. T. C. BROWNLEE, R. D. TOPSOM and R. W. TAFT, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1976, 98, 3020.
10. W. J. BEHRE, R. W. TAFT and R. D. TOPSOM, *Prog. Phys. Org. Chem.*, 1976, 12, 159.
11. C. G. SWAIN and E. C. LUPTON, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1968, 90, 4328.
12. G. M. BODNER and L. J. TODD, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1974, 13, 360.
13. D. R. COULSON, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1976, 98, 311.
14. M. GODFREY, *J. Chem. Soc., Perkin Trans. 2*, 1977, 769.
15. F. HRUCKA, H. M. HUTTON and T. SCHAEFER, *Can. J. Chem.*, 1965, 43, 2392.
16. W. B. SMITH, A. M. IHRIG and J. I. ROARK, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1970, 74, 812.
17. M. J. S. DRWAR, R. GOLDEN and J. M. HARRIS, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1971, 93, 4187.
18. D. A. DAWSON and W. F. REYNOLDS, *Can. J. Chem.*, 1975, 53, 378.
19. W. F. REYNOLD and G. K. HAMKE, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1976, 98, 7295.
20. J. BROMILOW, R. T. C. BROWNLEE, D. J. CRAIK, M. SADEK and R. W. TAFT, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1980, 45, 2419.
21. S. N. SAWHNEY and D. W. BOYKIN, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1979, 44, 1137.